

Morphological and Functional Zones of Beed Town: A Study in Urban Geography

S.B. Ashture

Head, Dept. of Geography, Shri Kumarswami Mahavidyalaya, AUSA Dist. Latur

Email; sbashture@gmail.com

Abstract: Urban geography refers the town as a dwelling place whose residents are mainly engaged in industry, household industries, retail trade, wholesale trade, transport and communication. Urban areas have been identified as centers of social change, attitudes, values and behavior patterns. It is characterized by its size, its density and the heterogeneity of its inhabitants and then spread to the rest of the population by process of diffusion through the urban system. Morphology of a town is concerned with the ground build and skyline of the houses. The plan may be internal which concerns with the arrangement of streets, and built space. Urban centers being the focus of human population perform certain essential functions. These functions are naturally influenced by the site, situation and environmental conditions of urban centers in which they are located. The functional interpretation of towns has become significant aspect of urban study as it provides a good basis for the regional planning.

Key words: Urbanization, functions, morphology.

1.1 Introduction:

Urban geography is recently developed branch of settlement geography as well as human geography relates towns and cities. The places in which most of the people engaged in secondary, tertiary and quaternary activities are known as urban centers. Urban geography refers the town as a dwelling place whose residents are mainly engaged in industry, household industries, retail trade, wholesale trade, transport and communication. Urbanization is interpreted as a process involving the absolute and relative growth of towns and cities within a defined area. Urban areas are characterized by structural change and foci of exchange processes. Urbanization is a behavioral process. Urban areas have been identified as centers of social change, attitudes, values and behavior patterns. It is characterized by its size, its density and the heterogeneity of its inhabitants and then spread to the rest of the population by process of diffusion through the urban system. A.E. smiles noted (1975) that, "Urbanization is the process whereby land and inhabitants become urban. According to G.S. Gosal "Urban geography is the geographic study of urban places which evolve, grow and exist as service centers for their surrounding areas".

1.2 Study Area:-

For the study of Morphological and Functional Analysis of Urban Centres, the Beed town is selected. It is a headquarters of Beed district of Maharashtra state and Class I town of the study area. Its latitudinal extension of the town is 18° 58' 14" north to 19° 00' 42" north and longitudinal extension is 75° 44' 10" east to 75° 46' 37" east. The municipal area of the town is 59.44 area in square kilometer and population according to 2011 census is 2,03,240 persons.

1.3 Objectives of the study:-

1. To analyze and explain the functional characteristics of the urban centers in study region.
2. To study the morphological structure of the urban centers.

1.4 Database and Methodology:-

Secondary data has been obtained from socio-economic reviews of the districts, district census handbooks, gazetteer, district town planning reports, reference books, journals, news papers, web-sites, etc.

Nelson's method has been used for functional classification of urban centers. In this method mean and standard deviation have been calculated. Standard Deviation is calculated by using following formula.

$$S.D. = \sqrt{\frac{\sum d^2}{N}}$$

Whereas:

S.D. = Standard Deviation

\sum = Sum

d = Difference between each value and mean

N = Total number of functions.

S.D. is added in mean and compared with regional mean to classify the towns.

1.5 Morphology of Beed Town :

The total area within the Beed Municipal limit is 820.00 hectares. Out of which 46.01 % is developed area in existing land use and in proposed land use it is 92.86 %. (Table No. 5.1 & Fig. No. 5.1, 5.2) The breakup of existing land use shows that 22.17 % area is under residential use, 1.46 % area is under commercial use, 0.81 % area is under industrial use, 11.73 % area is under transport and

communication use, 1.58 % area is under public and semi public amenities use, 7.21 % area is under public utility use and 1.05 % area is under open spaces and play ground etc. use of the total municipal area

1.6 Functional Zones of Beed Town :

1. Residential Area :

In the existing land use, area under residential use in the town is 798.51 hectares i.e. 24.52 percent of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in

proposed land use 2019.83 hectares area is allocated to residential use which is 62.03 percent to total municipal area. As per 2011 census, there were near about 40,060 houses existing in Beed city.

2. Commercial Area :

In the existing land use, area under commercial use is 11.99 hectares i.e. 1.46 % of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed land use 16.42 hectares area is allocated to commercial use which is 2.01 % to total municipal area.

Table No. 1.1 Beed Town: Existing and Proposed Landuse

Sr. No	Land Use	Existing Land use		Proposed Land use	
		Area in Hectares	% to total Municipal Area	Area in Hectares	% to total Municipal Area
1	Residential	181.77	22.17	381.00	46.46
2	Commercial	11.99	1.46	16.42	2.01
3	Industrial	6.63	0.81	20.80	2.54
4	Transport & Communication	96.18	11.73	192.21	23.44
5	Public & Semi- Public	12.92	1.58	31.55	1.69
6	Public Utility	59.15	7.21	80.31	9.79
7	Garden, Play Ground etc.	8.62	1.05	57.19	6.97
Total Developed Area		377.26	46.01	761.48	92.86
8	Agriculture	241.09	29.40	8.34	1.02
9	Water Bodies	57.24	6.98	50.18	6.12
10	Vacant & Barren Land	144.41	17.61	--	--
Total Undeveloped Area		442.74	53.99	58.52	7.14
Total Municipal Area		820.00	100%	820.00	100%

Source: District Town planning office, Beed District.

3 Industrial Land use:-

Industrial development in Beed city is in infancy due to non-availability of basic infrastructure facilities. In the existing land use, area under industrial use is 6.63 hectares i.e. 0.81 % of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed land use 20.80 hectares area is allocated to industrial use which is 2.54 % to total municipal area.

4 Transport and Communication:-

In the existing land use, area under transport & communication use is 96.18 hectares i.e. 11.73 % of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed land use 192.21 hectares area is allocated to transport and communication use which is 23.44 % to total municipal area.

Fig. No. 1.1 Beed Town: Existing and proposed Land Use

5. Public and Semi Public Area:-

In the existing land use, area under public & semi public amenities is 12.92 hectares i.e. 1.58 % of the total municipal area. By considering the future growth of the town, in proposed land use 31.55 hectares area is allocated to public & semi public amenities use which is 1.69 % to total municipal area. Nursing Homes, 11 Homeopathy, 17 Ayurvedic, 02 charitable hospitals in the Beed town. Government Hospital is located at Balbhim College road and left side to the Barshi road in Beed town. There are a minimum 380 medical shops in the Beed town. There are 63 primary schools at Beed town. Out of the 18 primary school are a Govt. primary school and other 45 school are a private school.

During 2012, there were six (6) Arts, commerce & science colleges are run by private institution. There is other 07 professional colleges (2 Engineering colleges, 1 Low colleges, 4 B.C.A./ B.C.S. Colleges) in the town.

1.7 Conclusion:-

Morphological study of towns essentially consists of the study of the pattern, internal functional arrangement and external form of the towns. Morphological and functional analysis of urban centers provides wide range of information about the process of urbanization which is very useful in the planning process of urban centers in particular and regional development in general

There is 1 government hospital, 13 BMC dispensaries, 63 Private Hospitals, 28 Private

1. Analysis of morphology of towns reveals that the town plans are influenced by natural and cultural factors. Among the natural factors relief and rivers play a very important role. The cultural factors affecting morphology includes, forts, temples, mosques, roads, railway station, administrative and public buildings.

2. The morphological study shows that there is a great variation in land use pattern from town to town. Maximum land of urban centres of the study area is found either under agriculture, residential and transport and communication use.

3. The external forms of towns of the study area are influenced by physical sites and socio-economic factors. These factors control the layout, functional morphology and external forms of the towns.

4. The morphological characteristics of urban centers in the area indicate that with the expansion in size and population of town, their morphological set-up also changes.

1.8 References:-

1. **Ahmad, E. (1958)** : 'Geographic Outline of Chota Nagpur Geographical Out Look, Vol.II, No.III, P.17
2. **Brush, J. E. (1968)**: 'Spatial Pattern of Population in Indian Cities.' Geographical Review, Vol. 58, PP.362-391.
3. **Burgess and Bogue, D.J.(Ed.), (1964)** : Contributions in Urban Sociology, University of Chicago.
4. **Dande, V. C. (March, 2011)** : "Morphological Study of AUSA Urban Centre, "Universal." Vol. No. Iii, Pp. 51-57.
5. **Dutta, K. L. (1968)** : 'Morphology of Indian Cities, Ph.D. Thesis Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi.
6. **Harris, C.D. and Ullman, E.L. (1945)** : " The Nature of Cities," Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Sciences. Vol 242.
7. **Taneja, K. (1971)** : 'Morphology of Indian Cities', National Geographical Society of India, Varanashi, P.52